

Analysis for LHC experiments at CERN

Executive Summary

Dirk Duellmann¹, Bernd Panzer-Steindel¹, Markus Schulz¹, Andrea Sciabà¹,
and David Smith¹

CERN, Geneva, Switzerland

1 Introduction

Physics analysis at CERN relies on a variety of hardware resources and software tools, with interactive usage becoming more common. This led to the question whether the current system is adequate to the needs of Run 3. This report is a short summary of a longer document [1] containing the results of detailed analysis I/O performance studies and its conclusions. The reader is referred to the full document for details.

2 Current analysis resources

Computing resources available for physics analysis activities at CERN have different forms and can be grouped in three categories: Grid-accessible resources, batch resources (LXBATCH) and interactive resources (LXPLUS, Spark/YARN, SWAN, dedicated high performance nodes).

In order to quantify the utilisation level of these resources, we considered reference periods in October 2021 of 7-10 days, for ATLAS and CMS. The information extracted by the relevant monitoring systems showed very clearly that the vast majority of analysis is non-interactive, with several thousands of CPU cores being used at any time in the Grid and batch resource pools, compared to a maximum of $O(100)$ cores being allocated by interactive analysis, and often at a very low level of utilization. This is already a strong indication that today any optimisation effort is best focused at batch analysis, though it is understood that this may change in the future, due to emerging analysis techniques which form the basis of an ever growing number of analysis facilities around the world.

3 Data access performance and EOS

In order to determine if analysis jobs are significantly constrained by I/O bottlenecks at the network or storage level when processing data on EOS, we conducted a detailed study of the EOS and LXBATCH log files for the period between February and May 2021.

The EOS logs contain detailed information about all data access operations. Only records related to users not doing organized processing and reading in

excess of 100 TB during that period were analyzed, under the assumption that they are likely to be “heavy” analysis users. This requirement selected O(100) users for ATLAS and CMS each, with a total read volume of 40 PB for ATLAS and 108 PB for CMS.

We measured the distributions of the read rates and found that they are dominated by small reads, with averages of 8 MB/s for ATLAS and 16 MB/s for CMS; only less than 1% of the transfers goes via the memory cache of the EOS servers. To obtain a reference value for the achievable throughput, we submitted thousands of trivial file copy jobs to LX BATCH. When using the EOS FUSE mount these reached an average of 80 MB/s and of 100 MB/s via the xrootd protocol. The comparison showed that the analysis applications were in no way limited by the EOS server capabilities, as confirmed also by the typically low number of file opens per second (mostly less than 20) and of seeks per file (less than 10). The large spread of read rates even for the case of the file copy application was confirmed to be due to disk contention, where several clients may access the same HDD drive at the same time.

A simple extrapolation of the EOS infrastructure scale to the beginning of the HL-LHC era in 2028 results in a doubling of the number of spindles, which does not radically change the picture.

The conclusion of this study was that EOS is working well below saturation with respect to the LHC analysis workload and that no obvious benefit would come from an additional HDD-based caching layer.

4 XCache data access performance

The second investigation we performed was intended to measure the performance and scalability of both SSD- and HDD-based XCache instances with respect to selected analysis workloads. We used a variety of benchmarks, ranging from synthetic benchmarks to real life analysis applications provided to us by ATLAS and CMS. The testbed consisted in a pair of nodes with 96 HDD of 12 TB each, a pair of nodes with 16 SSD of 2 TB each, and a number of client nodes. The two pairs were used to run XCache instances and each node has a 25 Gb/s connection.

Synthetic tests showed a sequential rate of 200 MB/s for HDDs, a maximum IOP of 200 for HDDs and 4500 for SSDs using random access; at the node level, the aggregate data rate is about 6.7 GB/s, not far from the limit imposed by the PCIe bandwidth.

A second type of benchmarks was used to reproduce realistic I/O patterns using a tool called MockData. We replayed file access from a 6-month period at the Prague ATLAS site, via XrdCl (the C++ xrootd interface). This benchmark produced drastically different results for the HDD-based XCache, with 1.2 GB/s, and for the SSD-based XCache, with 6 GB/s. Not surprisingly, I/O-heavy applications perform much better when reading data from SSDs.

The third type of benchmarks is based on actual analysis workloads, provided as representative examples by CMS and ATLAS. The *aggregate gradients* work-

load is a multithreaded ROOT script running on a 1.5 TB dataset composed of 189 files; *cms-skimmer* is a CMSSW-based analysis running on 640 NANOASIM files, and finally *top-xaod* is a workload reading a single DAOD_PHYS file of 1.16 GB, of which 256 copies were created. The workloads were run against a local filesystem (SDD or HDD-based) and an XCache instance (SSD or HDD-based). Each workload has different features and the results can be briefly summarized as follows:

- *aggregate gradients* is very I/O-intensive, but it can reach 60-70% of the maximum bandwidth for a local filesystem and approach the network limit for an XCache instance, with no large performance differences between SSD and HDD-based instances.
- *cms-skimmer* has a much lower I/O rate and shows almost no difference in performance when running against EOS and an XCache instance.
- *top-xaod* has minimal I/O rates and performs equally well for all storage configurations.

Storage scalability was studied using *cms-skimmer* in the simple case of one HDD in XCache hosting all input files. We saw that increasing the disk utilization up to saturation by increasing the number of clients causes the network rate to reach a maximum and then degrade, while the client CPU efficiency quickly degrades. We also estimated the maximum number of clients that could be served by an XCache instance for each workload, considering both the network and the storage device limitations, showing that such number can vary by orders of magnitude for different workloads, ranging from a few tens for *aggregate gradients* to tens of thousands for *top-xaod*.

These studies can be summarized by observing that the optimal storage configuration for analysis is critically dependent on the actual workloads; more specifically, an XCache instance is not always desirable, and solid state devices do not always provide a worthy performance advantage. The tests we performed should be considered just as examples, and further studies are needed to assess the benefits of different storage configurations in realistic applications.

5 Conclusions

The investigations we summarized here were aimed at determining if the current CERN infrastructure for analysis is adequate for the needs of the LHC experiments in the short term, and we did not find any bottlenecks that needed addressing before the start of Run 3, as the EOS servers operate well below saturation with the current hardware. In particular, there is no case at this point in time to deploy a caching layer or more performant storage. At the same time, it is well known that certain types of analysis applications are best served by high performance nodes and special storage configurations. Such nodes can, and are provided to experiments when needed and it is expected that they will become more relevant in the future.

References

1. Duellmann, D., Panzer-Steindel, B., Schulz, M., Sciabà, A., Smith, D.: Analysis for LHC experiments at CERN. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6337727>